

SOME DESIGN ASPECTS FOR MODERN AQUA-MEDIA CENTERS

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ABSTRACT

This article addresses the challenges and aspects of designing large water parks for a broader user base. It also examines the relevance of innovations in graphic design in relation to current trends in visual communications related to aquatic media centers.

Modern aqua -media centers have become increasingly popular among families and young adults. Many don't realize that many entertainment centers don't always use advertising and graphic materials correctly and effectively.

When a graphic revolution occurs, most people don't realize it and don't understand how to use its results to their advantage.

An aqua-media center is an entertainment complex featuring water play infrastructure and water attractions, such as water slides, splash pads , diving boards, fountains, a lazy river, and other water activities. The center also features minibars, cafes, and relaxation areas, ensuring a comfortable time for anyone and their family.

The Aqua Media Center is not only an entertainment complex, but also a modern 21st-century museum, equipped with everything you need for a comfortable leisure time.

At the design stage of the advertising and graphic presentation, the main goal was defined - to immerse the consumer in an unusual setting and the mysterious world of sirens, nagas , naiads and Medusa the Gorgon.

It's important to understand that designing a promotional and graphic presentation for an aqua -medi-center is a special branch of design in general. The presentation's primary goal is to illustrate actions and information in an accessible and clear manner, conveying the subject and objectives the designers set for themselves. The key characteristic and challenge of designing advertising posters is to convey the main idea embedded in the poster to the consumer in an accessible form. However, the key is the visual effects, which should not overwhelm the main information but rather enhance and highlight it in the best possible way.

Advertising and graphic presentation is a new, rapidly developing field of design. It works hand in hand with graphic and industrial design, defining its own trends and guiding user interactions. The design of advertising and graphic presentations is particularly dependent on

the use of media within the environment. Most people identify various sources of information available to them in a given location, but the primary graphic sources are advertising banners and posters, websites, and mobile apps. Therefore, it's important to understand how to most ergonomically manage the space of various posters, banners, and advertising slogans on websites, portals, and mobile apps, taking into account the surface area where consumers' eyes interact with important and useful information, and much more.

A promotional graphic presentation requires a complete layout and user interaction with any medium, regardless of format. Development requires consideration of a wide range of factors, including seemingly insignificant ones: from the user environment and the type of electronic device to the methods of input and display of information. This also includes the development of graphic elements, fonts, and the selection of the right color palette.

First and foremost, a presentation is the user's interaction with the system through the graphic transmission of data on a poster, essentially a speech outline that shows the most important points, helping to convey a single message throughout the speech.

Despite the relatively recent emergence of advertising and graphic presentation, there are established principles and laws that must be followed to ensure a product is accessible to users and commercially successful. At this stage in the development of this field, the following design criteria and principles have emerged:

- the organization of the posters and other media components. All must be logically structured and interconnected;
- the unification of poster components and other media. This involves grouping logically related components (menus, forms);
- alignment of poster components and other media. A poorly designed graphic element cannot be useful to anyone;
- a unified style across components, a corporate set. Stylistic design plays a significant role, as it's what's remembered by the client;
- the presence of white space. This allows for information blocks to be separated, focusing attention on one thing at a time, and receiving information clearly and concisely.

A poster or other graphic medium created according to all the rules significantly increases the effectiveness of the resource and gives it competitive qualities.

Having become familiar with the general principles of designing advertising and graphic presentations and user interactions, we can conclude that this area of graphic design stands somewhat apart from others, which necessitates, in addition to the visual component of a graphic poster, the development of logical user journeys. Therefore, it is essential to thoroughly and thoughtfully study the information on the topic and strictly adhere to the principles outlined, as the design of advertising posters and other graphic media is intolerable.

During the pre-project analysis, it became clear that studying competitors was not enough.

An important component of the pre-project research in developing the design of the advertising and graphic presentation of the aqua -media center is also the study of the direction of graphic design at the end of 2018 and at the beginning of 2019, collecting information on current trends in graphic techniques today.

Having studied various articles, studies, and works in the field of advertising and graphic presentation and summarizing the analysis, we can highlight several aspects that are discussed in almost all sources:

Laconicism

Unlike websites, mobile apps, and other graphic elements designed for different target audiences, advertising and graphic presentations will most often be used on various media, such as advertising posters, pages in fashion magazines, the Internet, advertising posters and billboards, and brochures.[22]

Light and dark color schemes

Using light and dark color schemes helps to create visual effects that attract attention to the design.

However, careful consideration must be given to the combination of such solutions. Dark color schemes can create serious readability issues.

Color scheme

Like other elements of graphic design, the color scheme of an advertising and graphic presentation should be selected taking into account the context of the advertising media and the goals that the user sets for themselves.

Bright colors

Dull colors became the foundation of flat design, permeating various related disciplines. The increasing shift toward brighter colors is a continuation of the rejection of soft minimalism. As many brands compete for user attention, drastic, sometimes reckless, steps are needed to achieve greater success.

Bold typography

Despite images, pixel density and the number of colors on the screen remain the most effective and accessible way to convey information. Fonts and unusual spacing are essential between different images and text. After all, typography is the fundamental foundation of successful graphic design—the ability to combine functionality and aesthetics on any background. [24]

Sketch and hand-drawn illustrations

Unique graphics truly compel users to pay attention. Literally any kind of product or service presentation will require a consistent style, using hand-drawn illustrations or sketches. Whether it's a promotional cover for a new movie, magazine, or book poster, the best option is a combination of vector or hand-drawn images with photography. Hand-drawn illustrations will become a leading trend in graphic design.

Comic book style

Comics are a unique art form that straddles the boundaries of image and text. However, they are more closely related to neither illustration nor literary genres. This style is becoming so fashionable and distinctive in all new graphic design trends that a well-illustrated comic, or a part of one, can, to a certain extent, add uniqueness to any artistic poster and individuality to a corporate identity.

Elements of pop art

Pop art is an artistic style that focuses on the material phenomena of everyday life, including popular culture (where the word "pop" originates). Pop art was formed based on visual moments that bring joy and pleasure to people. Many traditional forms of art are aimed

at communicating with people on a visual level, evoking specific emotions. Elements of pop art and its unique, vibrant colors are undoubtedly in great demand in new graphic design trends, namely in the production of modern gift cards, badges, branded T-shirts, posters, and placards. [22]

Thus, all the listed rules will be used in further design, and also in order to more accurately reflect the design of the advertising and graphic presentation.

When designing a successful advertising and graphic presentation, it's essential to understand the specific audience for which the presentation is intended, as the image the designer creates is aimed at a specific target audience. When creating an advertising and graphic presentation, it's important to carefully consider what it should contain, what functions it should perform, and the audience for which it is being developed. The primary target audience is family vacationers, children, students, and adults, each with their own interests, principles, and preferences.

The most important thing is to determine the functions of the presentation and what they are needed for.

Emotional portrait of the audience

Having analyzed the target audience, we can conclude that they are men and women who follow the news and the latest trends. They utilize a variety of advertising opportunities. The advertising and graphic presentation is aimed at reaching married couples, children, and students.

This example helps us better understand the target audience and the task at hand. The main goal is to use accessible graphic language, without compromising the user experience, to help them better understand and retain the information they need to convey, and to show all the places that will be of interest to families, children, and students.

The main examples of advertising and graphic presentation can be considered in the examples of other aqua -media centers.

The main example discussed here is the Aphrodite Waterpark in Paphos, Cyprus. Paphos is part of a UNESCO World Heritage Site. Paphos was once the capital of ancient Cyprus, and today it has become one of the most worthy and beautiful resorts in the Mediterranean. Myths and legends abound here. According to ancient legends, Aphrodite, the goddess of love and beauty, was born from sea foam. Subsequently, it was decided to name the large waterpark "Paphos" Aphrodite Waterpark » (Paphos Aphrodite Waterpark). The main feature of this water park is its underwater slides and attractions set amidst a mountainous landscape and exotic gardens. The highlight is the unforgettable natural setting of the Aphrodite Waterpark. The water park features 23 slides: 15 for adults and 8 for children. The following conclusion can be drawn: the main focus of the graphic presentation of the Aphrodite Waterpark is the mythology of ancient Greek culture, which underpins the entire ideological component of the advertising campaign.

Another example is the Serena Water Park in Espoo, Finland. It is one of the largest water parks in Finland. The water park is located just 23 kilometers from central Helsinki. When guests enter this unique park, they are immersed in a true underwater kingdom. The number of water attractions is so extensive and extensive that a single day visit simply isn't enough. Serena Water Park is open year-round, but one of the best times to visit is summer, when all the attractions are available. However, in winter, the Serena Winter Ski Resort opens next to

the water park. Ski ("Serena Ski "). One can only imagine the impact this winter spectacle can make. The water complex's graphics emphasize immersing the audience in a mountainous landscape surrounded by pine forests.

Moreon , Moscow's largest water park , which boasts a vast territory capable of accommodating up to three thousand visitors. Located near the Yasenevo metro station, it covers an area of almost 6,000 square meters.

This wonderful water park features seven large slides suitable for both children and adults. Every year, Moreon Water Park welcomes and strives to accommodate everyone. Those who enjoy constant tension and intense emotions will love the Black Holes, and the Space Saucer will also lift their spirits. Those who prefer a more relaxed experience will be delighted to enjoy the Family Park. The water park also features a pirate-themed children's playground, where every child can feel like a true pirate. Moreon itself is unique, boasting a thermal complex with a variety of saunas, including Russian, Turkish, and Finnish saunas, a jacuzzi, and an ice grotto. Among Moscow's many water parks, Moreon is an affordable and accessible destination suitable for people of all income levels. Unfortunately, not everyone has the opportunity to visit the sea.

Thus, we can conclude that the Moreon water park combines the diverse cultures of various peoples from both the north and south, giving the water park its own advantages in the labor market. Therefore, the graphic design features elements and patterns specific to each culture.

Another example is the water park " Coco" Splash " on Koh Samui . Koh Samui is one of the most beautiful islands in Thailand.

The water park offers virtually everything you need for a comfortable vacation: long beaches, the hot waters of the Gulf of Thailand, exotic wildlife, coral reefs, a colorful underwater world, and, of course, the water park itself.

Samui is not very large and is called " Coco" Splash ." Most tourists staying on Koh Samui express their dissatisfaction, thinking that the water entertainment complex is more intended for children. At the Coco water park Splash features a large water slide, reaching a height of almost 8 meters. The water park also features a blue slide made of solid concrete that gently takes you down, taking you around unusual turns. For those who prefer a more extreme experience, there are races where you can compete with friends for both time and speed on the two-lane " Multi-Slide ." Looking at all the unusual slides, you begin to realize that something is wrong with the water park. But the main idea of the water complex is that all the water slides " Coco" Splash " are made of concrete. As you can see, the main focus of the water park " Coco" Splash » is committed to the safety and peace of mind of tourists.

It can now be definitively concluded that the graphic design of the water complex embodies a specific idea and concept, encompassing several aspects: minimalism, functionality, and simplicity. This provides the water park with the key to immersing visitors in a calm, relaxed atmosphere.

Another example is the Chinese water park, Chang Long Water World, in Guangzhou. It is the largest water park in Asia, located in Guangzhou and known as Chang Long Water World. Despite this, the water complex is the fifth most visited attraction in the world, covering over 400,000 square meters. In 2007, this water park was awarded the International Association of Amusement Parks and Attractions' "Must-See" award for tourists worldwide. Guangzhou is

located in the south of mainland China and borders the South China Sea. Therefore, every year, Chang Long Water World is always warm and humid. Guangzhou is an ancient city with its own history and many diverse attractions. It was here that the Great Silk Road began. The number of tourists in Guangzhou grows every year. Chang Long Water World always welcomes approximately 40,000 people. It boasts the world's largest "Lazy River," stretching over 5 kilometers. While cruising down the river, you can explore the entire vast water park, while also experiencing numerous challenges: an ice room, numerous waterfalls, choppy water, artificial waves, and bridges. While cruising down the river, you can enjoy the experience not only alone or with just one other person, but also with a group. The Chang Long Water World entertainment complex in Guangzhou is a large water park boasting a variety of water slides and attractions of varying shapes, lengths, and heights.

In conclusion, we can say that the graphic design of the Chang Long Water World water park maintains the classical Chinese style, imitating the Hawaiian style.

The most unusual example is the water park " Wild" Wadi » in Dubai.

Waterpark " Wild" Dubai's Wadi was established in 1999. It's not the largest, but it's popular and offers a wide selection of water slides and attractions, which change and are added every year, and all the water activities share the same route. Wild Water Park Wadi " has different sections of its own, each offering its own unique experience. The water complex also features high rises at the base of the slides, which begin with a rapid descent, followed by a steep tube with numerous turns. Then, after all this, comes a "flight" in complete darkness. You can experience and discover new emotions at the Wild water park. Wadi ". Also in the city of Dubai is the most "terrifying" slide, moreover, only in " Wild" Wadi ." The water park is responsible for the safety of its visitors. The water complex employs numerous lifeguards from various countries in Europe and Asia, and many visitors are prevented from accessing dangerous attractions. But despite all these rules, at Wild Water Park Wadi offers excellent recreational facilities for families, couples with children, and young people. There is no age limit for entry to the water entertainment complex.

Thus, the water park " Wild Wadi is aimed at a target audience of families with children, young adults, and young families. The main concept of the water complex is to transport guests to the well-known fairy tale "The Adventures of Aladdin." Therefore, the entire graphic design is inspired by Arabic motifs and shares common threads with the adventures of the fairytale character "Aladdin." Despite this, the water park is surrounded by a beautiful artificial oasis, which further enhances the experience and imbues the place with a magical, mysterious world.

As an example, we can cite the Yas water park WaterWorld » in Abu Dhabi (UAE)

The fake Yas Island is located thirty minutes from Abu Dhabi and fifty minutes from Dubai. In 2007, the investment company Aldar Properties " set a date for the island's creation and transformation into a major global tourism hub for car enthusiasts and competitive sports enthusiasts. By 2010, the Ferrari Park had been completed. World Abu Dhabi, which was entirely dedicated to the Ferrari company, which had the fastest roller coaster, and which was open to the Yas track Marina Circuit ." Since almost 2009, this location has hosted numerous competitions, including Formula 1 races. This water park not only has its own unique identity but is also considered unique.

This is the entertainment water complex " Yas" Waterworld is a phenomenon in the Arab world. It covers over 15 hectares and features some 43 attractions, five of which are unique.

The water park is based on a folk legend that pays tribute to pearling, which played a pivotal role in the country's history. The legend tells of a young girl, Dana, who sought the "Lost Pearl," which brings good fortune to both herself and the villagers who lived with her. After overcoming numerous obstacles, including the desert, where she found new friends among the animals, and a beautiful oasis, Dana retrieved her lost pearl. This enormous treasure, which measures 8 meters in diameter and is housed atop the tall Jebel Tower, is the source of her treasure. Dana, at the farthest point of the water park. Now, this "lost pearl" has become the main calling card of Yas Island. You can create many unforgettable memories at this place. At the Yas water complex Waterworld boasts the longest waterslide, measuring 300 meters. This slide is considered the longest attraction in an Abu Dhabi water park and in the UAE.

Also in the water complex "Yas At Waterworld", you can create water battles. All you need to do is purchase pearl-shaped balls and stage a real competition with your family or friends. Young couples who have recently started a family have special offers from the water complex.

At the Yas Water Park At Waterworld in Abu Dhabi, you can become a real pearl diver. Guests dive with divers to a specific depth to select the desired shell. After catching the shells, you can ask a specialist to open a magical prize to see if it contains a pearl. If the shell contains a pearl, you can do anything with it: set it in a ring, a pendant, or make a bracelet. Knowing this, many tourists visit the water park solely to find real pearls. It is one of the most popular attractions in the UAE and is called Khoyamal.

In conclusion, it can be said that the water park's graphic design concept was based on folk history, which became a key factor in the popularity of this water complex. The entire design is dedicated to pearl fishing and features various fortresses with their own water attractions. But the main feature is the water slides, designed in the image of a snake's head.

This design project for the development of an advertising and graphic presentation for an aqua-media center was created to present a new modern graphic design.

During the design project, theoretical sources such as scientific literature, technical and methodological references, as well as analog studies and pre-project situation analysis, were analyzed. Synthesizing these sources led to the formulation of conclusions, which were used to formulate the concept for this project.

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